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QUALITATIVE STUDY OF DRINKING WATER OF VARIOUS SOURCES OF CHOUTAIR VILLAGES DISTRICT ZIARAT BALOCHISTAN, PAKISTAN

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Article info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 17 Sep 2023 Accepted: 07 Nov 2023</p> <p>Keywords Heavy metal, Microbes, Physicochemical parameters, Total Dissolved Solids</p> <p>Ahmad et al., (2023). Qualitative study of drinking water of various sources of choutair villages district ziarat balochistan, Pakistan: <i>J. S. Agri. Enviro. Sci</i>, 1(2), 43-55. https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5636-4593</p> <p>Copyright©2023 JSAES *Corresponding author Noor Ahmed Email: noortareen734@gmail.com</p> <p>Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.</p> <p> This content is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0)</p>	<p>ABSTRACT</p> <p>Water is a critical element for all forms of life, serving as the cornerstone for the survival of humans, animals, plants, and microorganisms. Across the globe, water contamination specifically from heavy metals and harmful microbes poses a severe risk to these living organisms. Safe and clean water is therefore non-negotiable, especially for residents of Balochistan, who primarily depend on springs and open wells for both agricultural and drinking needs. In an investigation focused on Ziarat District in Balochistan, water samples from various sources in the village of Choutair were examined for microbial contamination, heavy metal presence, and other physicochemical attributes. A total of 27 samples were collected from springs, open wells, and tube wells in Choutair, Ziarat, and Tandwani villages. The study's findings were concerning, particularly regarding coliform bacteria levels in the tested water samples. These ranged from 2.32 to 19.33 MPN/100ml, far exceeding the World Health Organization's (WHO) acceptable limit of zero Colony Forming Units (CFU). Additionally, E. coli levels in spring water were measured between 2.00 to 2.33 MPN/100ml, which is also higher than WHO guidelines. Heavy metals like Cadmium were found slightly above WHO's permissible levels, while lead levels were within acceptable limits. The study also assessed other physicochemical properties such as pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), and Turbidity, all of which fell within WHO's acceptable standards. The water in this region, particularly concerning coliform and Cadmium levels, poses a significant health risk and is unsuitable for human consumption or use in food industries.</p>

1. INTRODUCTION

Water stands as an indispensable and precious natural asset in our world. It's a fundamental element for all forms of life, ranging from microscopic organisms and simple plant life to complex biological systems like humans and animals (Onifada et al. 2008). The absence of water makes life unsustainable on our planet (Hussain. J et al. 2012). Indeed, water serves as an essential resource on Earth's surface. Ensuring its purity, particularly for drinking, is critical for human health. The degradation of water quality often stems from its misuse in agricultural, residential, and industrial contexts. Such degradation is manifested through a variety of contaminants, including both microbiological and chemical elements. These pollutants have widespread health implications (Adhena et al. 2015) and negatively impact both aquatic ecosystems and human well-being (Ezemonye et al. 2005).

Water borne disease are a significant global health concern. Roughly 4.3 billion instances of diarrhea are reported annually, and nearly 4.6% of the world's waterborne diseases were recorded in the year 2000 (WHO, 2002). In Pakistan alone, the annual number of diarrheal incidents is around 100 million (Daud M.K et al. 2017). Heavy metals (HMs) pose another problem as they are non-biodegradable and accumulate in the food chain. While certain metals like copper, zinc, and iron are essential in small quantities, they become detrimental when ingested in large amounts (Kar et al. 2008). Water tainted with such contaminants can lead to a range of health issues, including but not limited to, diarrhea, heart issues, nervous system disorders, and dental issues (Johnson & Hallberg., 2005). High levels of heavy metals can even result in permanent brain damage. Infants are particularly at risk since they consume more food relative to their body weight, making them susceptible to diseases like learning

disabilities, nervous system damage, and behavioral issues such as hyperactivity (Rajendran et al. 2003).

According to guidelines from the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, the acceptable level of lead in potable water is capped at 0.006 mg/l (Tareen A.K et al. 2014). Baluchistan holds the title for being Pakistan's most expansive province in terms of land area (Ahmed et al. 2014). Nearly 54% of its regions are irrigated using surface water, while underground water sources account for the remaining 46% (Ahmed S. 2007). Activities like deforestation and industrial development have significantly impacted both ground and surface water quality (Bhalme et al. 2012). In Ziarat District of Baluchistan, agriculture is the primary livelihood, and the main water sources are springs and open wells. With the water table declining in this specific area, the likelihood of elevated levels of heavy metals is increasing. The inhabitants of Balochistan predominantly reside near rivers and streams to access water for both irrigation and consumption (UNICEF, 2017). To safeguard against such water-related risks, it is essential to categorize the extent and origin of potential contaminants (Ushie et al. 2008). The present study aims to evaluate the drinking water quality in Ziarat District, Balochistan, focusing on its physicochemical, microbial, and heavy metal characteristics.

2. METHODOLOGY

The study aimed to assess the microbial composition, heavy metal levels, and physicochemical properties of drinking water from various sources in the Choutair village, located in the Ziarat district of Balochistan. Water specimens were gathered from multiple locations within the district of Ziarat (as indicated in Table 1). To minimize the potential for contamination, samples were collected in polyethylene bottles and accurately labeled.

2.1. Sampling

Water specimens were gathered from three distinct locations within Ziarat district, as shown in Table 1. These samples were stored in 250 ml plastic bottles and later analyzed at the Quetta research facility of the Pakistan Council of Research in Water Resources (PCRWR).

Table. 1 Name of Sampling areas, sources with their samples.

Samples	Sources	Area
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ZT	Tube well	Ziarat city
ZB	Bore	Ziarat city
ZS	Spring	Ziarat city
CT	Tube well	Choutair village
CB	Bore	Choutair village
CS	Spring	Choutair village
TT	Tube well	Tandwani village
TB	Bore	Tandwani village
TS	Spring	Tandwani village

2.2. Assessment of Physiochemical Characteristics

The physiochemical properties of the water specimens were evaluated according to the guidelines set forth by Joshi et al. (2009). The following parameters were assessed:

2.3. PH Levels

The pH level of each water sample was ascertained using a Jenway model 3520 pH meter, adhering to the general procedure outlined by AOAC (2012).

2.4. Electrical Conductivity (EC)

The electrical conductivity of the water specimens was measured with an LF-91 EC meter, following the standards established by AOAC (2012).

2.5. Measuring Turbidity

A Wag-WT-300 Nephelometer was used to assess the water's turbidity, in compliance with AOAC's 2012 standards.

2.6. Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

TDS levels were gauged using a TDS meter from HACH COISO USA, according to the AOAC 2012 standards.

2.7. Microbial Analysis Using the MPN Method

The microbial content, including total coliforms and E. coli, was evaluated in the water specimens using the Most Probable Number (MPN-9221) technique. For bacterial culturing, 4 grams of MacConkey broth were dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water. The broth was then dispensed into 15 test tubes containing inverted Durham tubes and sterilized at 121°C for 30 minutes. Water specimens of varying volumes were added to the tubes, which were then incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. Positive cultures were counted and cross-referenced with MPN tables as described by Tandon (2005).

2.8. Preparing Samples for Heavy Metal Analysis

The water specimens were subjected to a digestion process involving a mixture of concentrated HCl and HNO₃. After heating and cooling, the solution was filtered and

diluted with deionized water to a final volume of 100 ml, as guided by Fong SS et al. (2006).

2.9. Stock Solution for Lead Analysis

A stock solution containing 1000 mg/l of lead was prepared by dissolving 1.59 grams of lead nitrate in a 1% v/v HNO₃ solution, which was then diluted to one liter.

2.10. Stock Solution for Cadmium Analysis

A stock solution with 1000 mg/l of cadmium was formulated by dissolving 1.00 gram of cadmium in a minimum volume of 1+1 HCl, then diluting it to one liter using 1% v/v HCl.

2.11. Heavy Metal Analysis

The levels of cadmium (Cd) and lead (Pb) in the water samples were analyzed using an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Model Perkin Elmer 3280 USA), in accordance with the guidelines provided by Alzrog AM et al. (2013).

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1. Physicochemical Characteristics

3.1.1. PH Levels

The data displayed in Table 1 shows the variability in pH levels of water gathered from various locations within District Ziarat, Balochistan. pH serves as a crucial indicator for gauging the acidic or alkaline conditions of water. Maintaining a balanced pH is vital for human health and metabolic activity. The maximum pH level recorded was 7.76 ± 0.05 in the bore water from Tandiwani village, while the lowest was 7.42 ± 0.13 from the tube well water in Ziarat city. Average pH levels from different water sources were 7.51, 7.57, and 7.62NS, and across different regions were 7.49, 7.54, and 7.67NS. These findings align with the World Health Organization's (WHO) recommended pH range of 6.5 to 8.5 (WHO, 1993).

Water near industrial areas like mines, chemical waste sites, power plants, animal farms, and landfills tends to be more acidic. Such acidic water can leach metals like manganese, lead, iron, zinc, and copper

from plumbing systems, leading to various health issues such as stomach irritation and vomiting. Conversely, water with a basic nature, often found where limestone or alkaline minerals are prevalent, generally doesn't pose health risks but may impart an unpleasant or soda-like taste (Shakirullah et al. 2006).

3.1.2. Electrical Conductivity (EC)

Table 1 also highlights the electrical conductivity (EC) of water samples collected from different parts of District Ziarat. EC is essentially a measure of how well a medium can conduct electrical currents. The presence of salts and dissolved solids in water leads to ionization, which in turn affects the water's electrical conductivity (Sivaraju H.P. 2012). The highest EC reading was 959.44 ± 1.24 $\mu\text{S/cm}$ in bore water from Tandiwani village, whereas the lowest was 389.25 ± 2.88 $\mu\text{S/cm}$ in tube well water from Choutair village. Average EC levels for various sources were 498.89, 540.05, and 859.74 $\mu\text{S/cm}$, and across different areas

were 516.09, 628.96, and 753.63 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. All the recorded EC levels fell within the WHO's acceptable range of 1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

While EC itself doesn't directly impact human health, it is often measured for various reasons, such as gauging the rate of mineralization and estimating the amount of chemicals needed for water treatment (Kavcar. P et al. 2009). Methods like Reverse Osmosis (RO) and microfiltration are commonly used to reduce the EC levels by removing dissolved solids and colloidal materials (Azrine et al. 2011).

3.1.3 Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

The information presented in Table 1 highlights the levels of Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) in water gathered from various locations in the Ziarat District of Balochistan. TDS serves as a useful measure of water quality as it directly impacts the water's visual clarity, thereby affecting its aesthetic appeal (Vaidya S.R; Labh S.N. 2017). The study revealed that TDS levels were highest in the open well water in Tandiwani village, registering at 616.33 ± 0.88 mg/L. Conversely, the lowest concentration, 247.33 ± 0.88 mg/L, was observed in the tube well water from Choutair village. Average TDS levels varied between 318.44 and 551.22 mg/L for different water sources and ranged from 329.89 to 481.22 mg/L across various areas. While elevated TDS levels are typically not a health concern, they can pose risks for individuals with specific

medical conditions such as heart and kidney diseases (Vaidya S.R; Labh S.N. 2017). The World Health Organization (WHO) sets the acceptable TDS limit at 1000 mg/L, and the study found that all tested samples fell within this standard.

3.1.4 Turbidity

Table 1 also outlines the turbidity levels in water samples collected from diverse areas in Ziarat District, Balochistan. Turbidity refers to the water's cloudiness, which is influenced by various suspended particles (Hammer, 1986). Factors contributing to high turbidity include the presence of fine particles like silt, clay, as well as organic and inorganic substances. Elevated turbidity levels can impede water treatment processes and create an environment conducive to microbial growth, thus increasing the risk of waterborne diseases. In this study, the maximum turbidity level, 4.40 ± 0.33 NTU, was found in spring water from Choutair village. The minimum level, 2.97 ± 0.44 NTU, was recorded in an open well in the same village. The average turbidity ranged from 3.55 to 4.28 NTU for different sources and 3.84 to 4.16 NTU for various sites. The WHO recommends a maximum turbidity level of 5 NTU for potable water (WHO, 2011), and all the water samples in this study met this criterion. Various techniques like Reverse Osmosis (RO), ultrafiltration, settling, and decanting are effective in reducing water turbidity.

Table 1. Physicochemical parameters of drinking water of selected areas and sources of district Ziarat (Baluchistan).

Parameters	Source	Area			Mean	WHO Standard
		Ziarat	Choutair	Tandwani		
pH	Tube well	7.42 ± 0.13 NS	7.57 ± 0.14 NS	7.56 ± 0.23 NS	7.51 NS	6.5-8.5
	Bore	7.56 ± 0.17 NS	7.53 ± 0.22 NS	7.76 ± 0.05 NS	7.62 NS	
	Spring	7.49 ± 0.15 NS	7.51 ± 0.26 NS	7.71 ± 0.07NS	7.57 NS	
	Mean	7.49 NS	7.54 NS	7.67 NS		
Electrical conductivity (EC)	Tube well	766.78 ± 2.65 C	389.25 ± 2.88 H	464.11 ± 1.46 F	540.05 B	1200 (µS/cm ³)
	Bore	872.44 ± 1.24 B	747.33 ± 2.60 D	959.44 ± 1.24 A	859.74 A	
	Spring	621.67 ± 5.36 E	411.67 ± 1.95 G	463.33 ± 3.29 F	498.89 C	
	Mean	753.63 A	516.09 C	628.96 B		
Total Dissolves Solid (TDS)	Tube well	489.67 ± 2.03 C	247.33 ± 0.88 H	298.67 ± 1.76 F	345.22 B	1000 mg/l
	Bore	558.67 ± 2.19 B	478.67 ± 0.66 D	616.33 ± 0.88 A	551.22 A	
	Spring	395.33 ± 1.76 E	263.67 ± 0.66 G	296.33 ± 1.20 F	318.44 C	
	Mean	481.22 A	329.89 C	403.78 B		
Turbidity	Tube well	4.13 ± 0.08 A	4.13 ± 0.26 A	4.30 ± 0.26 A	4.28 A	5 (NTU)
	Bore	4.00 ± 0.05 A	2.97 ± 0.44 B	3.67 ± 0.06 AB	3.55 B	
	Spring	4.33 ± 0.24 A	4.40 ± 0.33 A	4.30 ± 0.26 A	4.26 A	
	Mean	4.16 A	3.84 A	4.09 A		

3.1.5. Sources of Heavy Metals in Drinking Water

Water can be contaminated with hazardous metals and minerals from both natural and man-made origins. Natural sources include sedimentary rock seepage, forest fires, and volcanic eruptions. On the other hand, human activities like industrialization significantly contribute to the presence of heavy metals in our drinking water. These toxic elements generally enter our system through contaminated food and water, and to a lesser extent, through the air we breathe. The use of cosmetics, paints, lead-acid batteries, coal-fired power plants, mining operations, and fuel burning are primary contributors to this issue.

3.2. Heavy Metal Analysis

3.2.1 Lead (Pb)

Data presented in Table 2 indicates the concentration levels of lead (Pb) in drinking water gathered from various locations in District Ziarat, Balochistan. Elevated levels of lead can be attributed to natural rock seepage, pipe corrosion, use of lead-based batteries, and paints, as well as coal-fired power plants and industrial waste (Uzma, I; Chandio T.A. 2017). The highest concentration of lead was found in tube well water in Tandwani Village, while the lowest was in the village's spring water. According to WHO guidelines, the safe

limit for lead in drinking water is 0.05 mg/L (WHO, 2011). Our findings show that all the sampled water was within this limit, suggesting it is safe for consumption. However, excessive lead exposure can have detrimental effects on the nervous system and is linked to certain cancers (WHO, 2011).

3.2.2 Cadmium (Cd)

Table 2 also shows the cadmium (Cd) levels in drinking water samples from different parts of District Ziarat, Balochistan. Cadmium primarily enters water systems through industrial waste, plastic disposal, coal burning, and automotive sources. It is recognized as a human carcinogen by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) (Godt J et al. 2006). Even in small amounts, cadmium can adversely affect kidney function and blood pressure (Rajappa B et al. 2010). The highest and lowest cadmium levels were found in tube well water in Choutair Village and bore water in Tandwani Village, respectively. The WHO's recommended cadmium limit in drinking water is 0.05 mg/L (WHO, 2011). Our study found that the cadmium levels in all samples exceeded the WHO guideline of 0.003 mg/L, making it unsafe for drinking. Immediate action such as water treatment and public awareness campaigns are essential.

Table .2 Heavy metals concentration (mg/l) of drinking water of selected areas and sources of district Ziarat (Baluchistan).

Heavy metals	Source	Area			Mean	WHO Standard
		Ziarat	Choutair	Tandwani		
Lead (Pb)	Tube well	0.0067 ± 0.00088 C	0.0400 ±0.030 B	0.00800 ± 0.0057 A	0.0422 A	0.05 mg/L
	Bore	0.0060 ± 0.0011 C	0.0097 ± 0.00088 BC	0.0333 ± 0.0088 BC	0.0163 B	
	Spring	0.0017 ± 0.00066 C	0.0047 ± 0.0057 C	0.0010 ±0.00057 C	0.0024 C	
	Mean	0.0048 C	0.00181 B	0.0381 A		
Cadmium (Cd)	Tube well	0.020 ± 0.0012 DEF	0.056 ± 0.0015 A	0.019 ± 0.00088 EF	0.032 A	0.003 mg/L
	Bore	0.022 ± 0.0012 D	0.018 ± 0.00088 F	0.010 ± 0.00082 G	0.017 B	
	Spring	0.035 ± 0.00088 C	0.042 ± 0.00082 B	0.021 ± 0.0013 DE	0.033 A	
	Mean	0.026 B	0.039 A	0.017 C		

3.3. Bacteriological examination of water samples from selected locations

3.3.1. Fecal Coliform Analysis

Table 3 presents data on the fecal coliform levels in drinking water gathered from various sectors of the Ziarat District in Balochistan. The primary reason for the microbial tainting of water is inadequate waste management practices. The presence

of coliform bacteria in drinking water is indicative of potential intestinal pathogens. Vulnerable areas where women and children collect water may also contribute to the microbial pollution of these sources (Shewaye M et al. 1999). Coliform bacteria are generally rod-shaped and predominantly gram-negative. They are mostly aerobic or facultatively anaerobic. The study found the highest fecal coliform

levels (19.33 ± 1.67 MPN/100ml) in Ziarat city's spring water, while the lowest (2.33 ± 1.20 MPN/100ml) were in Choutair village's bore water. The average coliform counts varied between different water sources and locations, ranging from 7.222 to 15.22 MPN/100ml and 6.89 to 12.89 MPN/100ml, respectively. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that drinking water should have zero CFU of coliform per 100ml (WHO, 2011). The findings indicate that all tested water samples exceeded the WHO's acceptable coliform levels, posing a significant health risk. Consequently, the water is unsafe for human use. Public education on boiling or filtering water to remove microbial contaminants, especially in spring water, is essential. The government must also conduct regular inspections, maintenance, and bacteriological testing of water sources to prevent any form of contamination.

3.3.2. Analysis of *Escherichia coli* Presence

Table 3 also reveals the range of *E. coli* levels in drinking water collected from various parts of the Ziarat District in Balochistan. Poor waste management is a leading cause of *E. coli* contamination in water supplies. *E. coli* is recognized as a significant contributor to hemorrhagic colitis and is usually transmitted through contaminated water or food (Bide P et al. 2005). The presence of *E. coli* indicates pollution from human or animal feces. This is a significant concern, especially in developing countries where the water quality is either good or moderate, yet other transmission routes for diseases like diarrhea, hepatitis, and typhoid exist (Kosek M et al. 2003). The study found *E. coli* levels ranging from 2.00 to 2.33 MPN/100ml, specifically in spring water. This level surpasses the WHO recommended limits of zero CFU per 100ml, highlighting a severe public health concern. Therefore, spring water in the area is unfit for human consumption. Government intervention is needed to direct spring water flow through pipelines to mitigate bacterial contamination.

Table .3 Microbe's analysis (MPN/100ml) of drinking water of selected areas and sources of district Ziarat (Balochistan).

Microbes	Source	Area			Mean	WHO Standard
		Ziarat	Choutair	Tandwani		
Total coliform	Tube well	5.67 ± 0.88 DE	4.667 ± 0.33 EF	11.33 ± 0.88 C	7.222C	0 CFU/100ml
	Bore	7.67 ± 0.88 D	2.33 ± 1.20 F	14.67 ± 0.88 B	8.22 B	
	Spring	19.33 ± 1.67 A	13.67 ± 0.88 BC	12.67 ± 0.33 BC	15.22 A	
	Mean	10.89 B	6.89 C	12.89 A		
E. coli	Tube well	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	0 CFU/100ml
	Bore	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	
	Spring	2.33 ± 0.33 A	2.00 ± 0.00 A	2.33 ± 0.33 A	2.23 A	
	Mean	0.78 A	0.67 A	0.78 A		

CONCLUSION.

The study carried out in Ziarat district of Balochistan focused on evaluating the quality and safety of drinking water. Pollution caused by harmful chemicals, including toxic substances from mining activities, combustion byproducts, as well as agricultural chemicals like fertilizers and pesticides, was identified. Specifically, the

levels of heavy metals such as cadmium were found to exceed the limits set by the World Health Organization (WHO). Furthermore, bacterial contamination was another significant concern. This contamination primarily stems from agricultural runoff, waste from animals, and both industrial and household waste. All water samples examined in the study showed fecal coliform levels that surpass

the acceptable standards. Additionally, the presence of E. coli bacteria was notably higher in spring water samples, exceeding WHO guidelines. This poses a substantial health risk to consumers. As a result, the water in the studied area is unsuitable for human consumption. Urgent actions are

needed, such as the installation of water treatment facilities and public education initiatives, to protect this critical freshwater resource. The government should also consider piping spring water from nearby areas to mitigate bacterial contamination.

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